

An Analogy Engine for a Generative Program Without Neural Networks

Generative AI as we know it grew out of the 2017 paper *Attention Is All You Need*, which proposed the Transformer architecture. As of 2026, following the arrival of ChatGPT in 2022, a wide range of generative AI services exists. I am one of their users, and I benefit practically from that research and its results. Yet in the course of using them, certain questions arise.

1. Why do hallucinations occur in the first place?
2. Why can these systems not actively critique, verify, or make proposals about the very framing a user presents?
3. How can reward optimization be prevented?
4. How could a generative AI make a meaningful “invention”?

I have come to suspect that these questions share a common root: the neural-network structure itself.

A neural network is like a rugged mountain whose terrain we cannot see. When we pour in the “water” of an input, it simply flows downhill toward the bottom — that is, toward the output — and there is no way to know the path the water took along the way. And even though it converges toward ones and zeros, the result is ultimately probabilistic: we receive only the nearest approximation, and it is hard to tell whether that is truly what I intended. Water poured onto a mountaintop simply runs down the fastest path that gravity allows. Generative AI is much the same: it merely advances toward its goal along the most efficient route and produces an output.

As I understand it, a neural network is closer to a structure in which linked sets of information, formed through training, switch on and off in isolated bursts. On the basis of this understanding, I strongly suspect that unless the user’s input itself provides a clue toward some new set of information, a generative AI will find it difficult to exceed a fixed limit — to go beyond the user’s input.

I therefore conjecture that generative AI hands us the most probable tool among those that already exist in the world, but does not create the tool itself and offer it to us. For that reason, I resolved to build a truly generative structure capable of invention.

One thing must be made clear here: I mean *invention*, not *creation*. Creation is making something out of nothing; invention is combining existing things to make a new thing. The boundary between creation and invention is a matter of philosophical debate, but at least the history of technology has been overwhelmingly one of “recombining what already exists.” It has always been a succession of discoveries and inventions, and by piling up that foundation we have reached the present state of humanity and its science and technology.

I therefore judged that the key lies in the mechanism by which humans invent.

In sum, in this essay I focus in particular on question 4, invention. I do suspect the other three share the same root, but since my clearest goal is a program that *invents*, I begin by examining question 4 and aim to resolve the remaining questions in turn.

Hypothesis. Human analogy is the “extraction of a recurring context,” and this can be implemented and observed — without a neural network — through distance computation over a holistic concept graph. I further conjecture that this analogy engine will be the basis of “invention,” but that lies outside the scope of this essay and is a domain not yet designed. The claim is falsifiable: if there exists a case in which a concept already explicitly defined at the level of analytic philosophy is handed to the analogy engine with its definition and structure intact, yet priming/inference/discrimination still fail to work, then this claim is broken. One caution: a concept that has *not yet* been defined provides weak grounds as a falsification condition. Such a concept is merely awaiting definition — this is not a declaration of vindication, but a matter to be held in reserve.

I first chose algebra as the domain in which to build a generative program, because verification there divides cleanly into right or wrong and the result is produced immediately.

I built a simple generative program together with an answer checker. At this point, thinking of the four basic arithmetic operations as my example, I chose “compression” as the tool for driving the expansion of concepts. The idea was not wrong in itself: multiplication is, after all, the efficient “compression” of repeated addition, and exponentiation is again the “compression” of multiplication.

But that idea was soon refuted. When I asked the system to reach and solve a nonlinear equation in algebra by way of the tool “compression,” it produced a wrong answer. I came to conclude that “compression” works only within a certain limited region. And right away, I began to wonder whether there were other concepts that — like “compression” — work only within a certain limited field.

An example came to mind quickly. I take the view that concepts qualify, contradict, and structure one another to form meaning. So, as something that shares the same kind of context as the “compression” of arithmetic, I settled on the *opposite* of a concept. Here I considered two possible cases: in the first, there is some underlying essence, and its facets are the representations that interlock and surface differently in each field; in the second, each field has its own fixed fundamental principle, which we merely discover.

But the assumption I came to focus on was a third case: that we *invent*, through analogy, the tool each field requires.

Indeed, analogy is widely accepted as one of the core capacities of human cognition (e.g., Gentner’s structure-mapping theory). Taking this as my starting point, I provisionally named the thing I was after a generative program to which the neural-network structure of generative AI is *not* applied, and I began working out how to implement the human mechanism of “analogy” within it.

First, the process by which “analogy” occurs must be taken apart. I do not regard “analogy” as the ability to conceive something out of nothing. Rather, where a certain context recurs, the ability to extract that context — that, I judged, is what “analogy” is. So I went on to consider how exactly humans, and I in particular, perform analogy.

Humans take in information from the world in diverse ways through five input organs, the five senses. From among the information taken in, I extract a context out of those things that share a common property. Then, in my head, I rapidly try random combinations to see whether there is some other field to which the extracted context can be applied. And when I finally find an applicable combination — eureka! This is precisely what becomes “analogy,” and “intuition.”

Laid out, the process I went through comes to four stages:

1. Random learning of information
2. Confirming and extracting a context from the random information
3. Trying random combinations to see whether the extracted context applies anywhere
4. When a combination emerges — eureka!

This strikes me as very similar to “invention.” Fire → heat and light; strong resistance + electric current → heat and light: the principle of the light bulb shares with fire the same context of “heat and light.” Ultimately, I conjecture that “analogy” is the basis of “invention.”

Here a problem arises. Humans gather diverse information through five input organs, but for a program whose input organs differ greatly from a human’s, I do not know how one could convey a concept that has been described in terms of human input organs.

Still, I have presumed that a person is connected to the whole of other concepts on the basis of either the minimal units of concepts (atomism) or combinations of opposing concepts (holism). Accordingly, I thought the dataset for the generative program should be built by inputting a vast multi-concept structure in which concepts are interconnected and interact — grounded either in atomism (e.g., the point) or in holism (concept pairs that qualify one another, such as good and evil).

At first I tried to build it on the basis of dictionary definitions, but I realized that dictionaries rely on a classificatory structure, and so I set my criterion as the *concept* instead.

Let me give, as an example, something I verified directly. By biological classification, a bat and a bird are a mammal and an avian. Mammals and birds are very distant concepts, branching apart back at Eukaryota → Animalia → Chordata. And yet people can draw an “analogy” between a bat and a bird, because both concepts share the property of “flight” (family resemblance).

From this I decided to build the dataset as a structure in which all concepts, grounded in holism, mutually describe, complement, and rebut one another like a spider’s web. (This web-structuring of concepts is itself a holism machine, hence mutually complementary.)

The web-structuring of concepts, I believe, can make verifiable what a neural network cannot verify. How far apart concepts lie becomes directly computable in terms of hops, and I expect that the process of how an analogy worked becomes precisely observable. (In fact, at toy scale I succeeded in tracing the verification; a large-scale experiment has not yet been attempted.)

There is a point to address here. What expresses a concept is, in the end, language. But language has many homographs. A simple example is the English word *bat*. *Bat* can mean the flying animal, but it can also mean a baseball bat. If what the user intends is the animal, then the baseball bat becomes noise. To address this, I aim to raise the precision of concept reference by introducing multiple languages. The moment English *bat* becomes Korean *bakjwi* (박쥐, the animal), the baseball *bat* of English disappears. Conversely, the Korean word *bae* (배) means the body's belly, the fruit pear, the multiplier "times" in mathematics, and the vessel "ship." Going to English, these become *stomach*, *pear*, *times*, and *ship* — distinguishable as separate words. This shows that introducing multiple languages is in fact bidirectional, and that taking the intersection lets us pinpoint the entity. In short, even though languages and vocabularies differ, taking their intersection lets us take aim at a fixed entity (again, succeeding at toy scale).

We should then also check when my claim would break. I have taken the side of holism. Atomism and holism are debated within analytic philosophy, but since this system grasps meaning as a role within a web, I judged holism to be the right fit. As it happens, I recently read a paper by the analytic philosopher Lee Jeong-gyu (Seoul National University), "What Is It to 'Sseom-ta'?": An Analysis of the Application Conditions of the Neologism 'sseom-tada'" (2019, KCI-indexed). In it, one can see the word "sseom-tada" decomposed and defined across twelve stages so as to leave no contradiction or possibility of rebuttal. I tried, on my own, to rebut it or to point out a contradiction as hard as I could, and I failed completely.

On the basis of that experience: if there exists a case in which a concept already explicitly defined by analytic philosophy is handed to the system with its definitional structure intact, yet priming/inference/discrimination still fail to work, then this claim is broken. As noted earlier, let us not forget that an undefined concept is subject to held-over verification.

There are also points that must clearly be acknowledged.

All verification so far has remained at toy scale. For this structure to carry real meaning, the following work lies ahead, and at present none of it has been undertaken.

1. Rather than a small, hand-built concept web, one must bring in actual large-scale concept data (e.g., an external commonsense graph) as is, and confirm that analogy works through the noise within it and that verification filters the noise out.
2. One must show — by measurement rather than by hypothesis — that the intersection of multiple languages actually cancels noise.
3. A concept web is easy at the lower layers but grows emptier toward the upper layers. Lower-layer concepts such as addition and multiplication accumulate easily, but upper-layer abstract concepts such as discrete mathematics or Bell's inequality have almost no connecting links in the web. I see this as a problem requiring an order of progressive conquest from lower to upper layers — that is, a curriculum. Indeed, in research on cognition and learning, the approach of learning from easier to harder (Curriculum Learning, Bengio 2009) is known to be more effective. That said, upper-layer concepts reside not in a commonsense web but in natural-language papers and textbooks, and

how to bring them into the web *without* using a neural network remains an unsolved problem.

And then the largest blank space remains. What I have built so far is the analogy engine — that is, a device that measures the distance between concepts and extracts context. The step that connects this to actual “invention” — the part that makes something new out of the context extracted through analogy — has not even been designed yet. The question 4, “invention,” that this essay took as its starting point has come only as far as setting up the skeleton of its prerequisite, the analogy engine; invention itself still remains an open task.

So by what, then, should we judge whether “invention” has occurred? As candidate criteria I thought of the three requirements of patent examination: novelty (not existing before), inventive step (not obvious), and utility (being useful). Since I defined invention as “combining existing things to make a new thing,” these three fit well. However, the three requirements differ in how objectively a machine can score them. Utility can be objectively judged by a verifier through “does the tool solve the problem”; novelty, too, can be partly mechanized through comparison against existing data. But inventive step (“is it non-obvious”) ultimately rests on the subjective judgment of a human examiner, and is hard for a machine to score objectively. In other words, judging “invention” objectively is itself difficult — and this is one of the core reasons the step connecting the analogy engine to invention is hard.